

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' LOGICAL THINKING THROUGH MECHANICAL PROBLEMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20304069>

Abstract. *The article highlights the methodology of developing logical thinking skills of senior class students of secondary schools through the process of solving problems in the mechanics' section of physics. The psychological-pedagogical foundations of logical thinking are analyzed, and the stages of forming analytical and synthetic thinking through mechanics' problems are developed. The study presents a five-stage algorithm for solving problems, heuristic methods, and ways to activate students' cognitive activity by creating problem situations.*

Keywords: *logical thinking, mechanics problems, physics education, analytical thinking, heuristic method, problem-based learning, problem-solving algorithm, cognitive activity.*

Introduction. One of the main goals of the modern education system is to form in students the skills of independent thinking, problem solving and application of acquired knowledge in practice. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the Concept of Education Development until 2030 set the priority task of increasing the intellectual potential of the younger generation and providing education based on a competency-based approach [Page 1].

One of the most important requirements for education in the 21st century is to arm the student not only with ready-made knowledge, but also to equip him with the skills of thinking, analyzing and drawing conclusions. Logical thinking is the central link in this process. The results of international studies such as PISA and TIMSS show that the indicators of our country's students in solving non-standard problems and analyzing data are still insufficient. This makes improving the methodology of teaching natural sciences such as physics an urgent task [Page 2]

Physics, in particular its mechanics section, has wide opportunities for the development of logical thinking. Mechanics problems require the student not only to memorize formulas, but also to analyze the situation, determine cause-and-effect relationships, put forward hypotheses and come to well-founded conclusions. Therefore, mechanics problems are recognized as an effective didactic tool for the formation of logical thinking.

This article discusses the methodology for the gradual development of students logical thinking by solving mechanics problems, its theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms [Page 5]

Main part. Logical thinking is the process of a person's perception of events using concepts, judgments and conclusions, identifying connections between them and generating new knowledge. In psychological and pedagogical literature, logical thinking is recognized as a form of higher cognitive activity of a person.

In the studies of scientists such as L.S. Vygotsky, J. Piaget, P.Ya. Galperin, V.V. Davidov, N.A. Menchinskaya, logical thinking was analyzed as the main indicator of the child's intellectual development. According to J. Piaget's theory of cognitive development, formal-operational thinking begins to form in adolescents aged 11–15, and it is during this period that the ability to work with abstract concepts, hypothetical-deductive thinking, and use logical operations appears.

Therefore, teaching physics, including the mechanics section, in grades 7–11 is the most favorable age for the development of logical thinking [Page 3,4,5,6,7].

There are the following basic operations (actions) of logical thinking:

- analysis – breaking down the whole into parts, studying the internal structure of a phenomenon;
- synthesis – combining the separated parts and recreating the whole;
- comparison – identifying similarities and differences between objects and phenomena;
- generalization – identifying common features common to many phenomena;
- abstraction – separating important features from unimportant ones;
- classification – dividing objects into groups according to their features;
- inference – generating new knowledge by inductive (from the specific to the general) and deductive (from the general to the specific) methods

In the process of solving problems in mechanics, all of these operations are manifested in an integral unity. This makes the mechanics section a holistic didactic tool for developing logical thinking.

Mechanics is one of the first and most fundamental branches of physics, which studies the laws of motion and interaction of bodies. The special role of mechanical problems in the development of logical thinking is explained by the following:

1) Mechanics phenomena are close to the student's everyday experience - they observe the movement, fall, and ejection of objects. This creates conditions for connecting theoretical knowledge with practice, that is, for synthetic thinking.

2) Mechanics problems in most cases require several logical stages: perception of the situation, modeling, selection of formulas, calculation, interpretation of the result.

3) In mechanics, a single phenomenon can be analyzed in various ways (kinematic, dynamic, energetic). This encourages the student to search for alternative solutions, perform comparison and selection operations.

4) Mechanics problems can be presented in various forms, such as graphs, tables, and drawings. This recoding of symbolic information forms an important skill of logical thinking.

The works of researchers V.G. Razumovsky, A.V. Usova, A.A. Boboyev, and others emphasize that the effectiveness of physics teaching is directly related to the student's level of independent problem solving [Page 10,11,12].

The process of solving a problem is the result of logical thinking in action. For the purposeful development of various operations of logical thinking, it is advisable to classify mechanical problems according to their didactic function. The author's classification is presented in the table below:

Table-1. Classification of mechanics problems according to logical operations

№	Issue type	Logical skill to be developed
1	Quality issues	Analysis, identification of cause-and-effect relationships
2	Calculation problems	Sintez, deduktiv xulosa chiqarish
3	Graphics issues	Abstraction, reading symbolic information

№	Issue type	Logical skill to be developed
4	Experimental issues	Inductive inference, hypothesis formulation
5	Problems with alternative solutions	Comparison, selection, evaluation
6	Problematic issues	Holistic logical activity, creative thinking
7	Combined issues	Classification, generalization

This classification allows the teacher to consciously choose the type of problem based on which logical operation is aimed at developing in each lesson.

To consistently develop logical thinking, it is necessary to divide the problem-solving process into clear stages and teach the student a specific mental action at each stage. The five-step algorithm proposed below activates a specific logical operation at each stage:

Stage 1. Perception and analysis of the problem.

The student carefully reads the problem, understands the essence of the physical phenomenon. At this stage, the following questions are asked: "What phenomenon is described in the problem? What objects are involved? In what state are they?". Logical operation - analysis.

Stage 2. Distinguishing between given and sought quantities, writing a short note.

The student translates textual information into a symbolic form: "Given: $v_0 = 0$, $a = 2 \text{ m/s}^2$, $t = 5 \text{ s}$. Find: $S = ?$ ". At this stage, abstraction and modeling operations develop.

Stage 3. Planning – developing a solution strategy.

The student plans what formulas to use, what laws to work with. If there is no formula directly, he thinks about how to find intermediate quantities. Logical operation – synthesis and deductive reasoning.

Stage 4. Implementation of the plan - calculation and obtaining the result.

The student performs calculations by substituting values into the selected formulas. Pays attention to units of measurement, accuracy of calculations. Logical operation - algorithmic thinking.

Stage 5. Checking and interpreting the result – reflection.

The student checks the physical content of the answer: "Is this number true? Are the units correct? Can the solution be found in another way?". It is this stage that forms critical and reflective thinking. Unfortunately, most students skip this stage, although it requires the highest level of logical thinking [Page 9]

Based on the above, the following heuristic methods are effective in developing logical thinking:

- 1) The "Backward" method - thinking from the beginning to the end. For example, what formula is needed to find the required quantity? Are the quantities involved in this formula given?
- 2) The "Schematic drawing" method - expressing the problem in the form of a graphic image. This makes an abstract situation visible.
- 3) "Boundary case analysis" - analyzing the problem in limiting cases such as $t = 0$ or $t \rightarrow \infty$. This is a powerful tool for checking the correctness of the answer.

4) The “Analogy” method - comparing a new problem with a previously solved similar problem. This activates the operations of comparison and generalization.

5) The “Problematic situation” method - bringing the student to a state of lack of knowledge and encouraging him to seek new knowledge from it. For example: “What will happen to the objects on it if the Earth suddenly stops?”

6) The “variation problem” method is a method of creating a new problem by slightly changing the conditions of a problem. This helps the student to understand cause-and-effect relationships more deeply.

Consistent use of these methods improves not only the student's physical knowledge, but also his general intellectual culture.

Below is an analysis of a qualitative-computational problem and logical reasoning in solving it.

Problem. A loaded wagon is moving along a straight line. A weight is located under a string hanging from one point of the wagon (mathematical pendulum). The pendulum is at rest. Suddenly the wagon begins to brake. In which direction does the pendulum deviate? Justify your answer.

Reasoning:

1) Let's analyze the situation: the speed of the wagon is decreasing, which means that the wagon has an acceleration directed opposite to the direction of movement ($a < 0$).

2) The pendulum is located in the frame of the wagon. The wagon is considered a non-standard (non-inertial) frame of reference, since it is moving with acceleration.

3) In a non-inertial frame of reference, the weight is affected by the inertial force. This force is directed opposite to the acceleration of the wagon, that is, in the direction of movement of the wagon.

4) Therefore, the pendulum deviates in the direction of movement of the wagon (forward).

5) Verification: we also know from everyday experience that when a bus brakes, the passengers inside tend to move forward. This is a typical manifestation of the phenomenon of inertia.

When solving this problem, the student performs logical operations such as analysis, deductive reasoning, building a physical model, and comparison with everyday experience.

The following criteria have been developed to assess the effectiveness of the proposed methodology:

- the level of correct understanding of the problem condition and the ability to independently compose a brief note;
- the ability to independently choose a solution algorithm;
- the ability to justify the answer from a physical point of view;
- the level of ability to solve problems with non-standard and alternative solutions;
- the ability to analyze one's own solution and find errors (reflexive thinking);
- the speed of assimilation of new knowledge and its application to new situations (transfer).

Diagnostic sections conducted according to these criteria allow an objective assessment of the effectiveness of the methodology [Page 12].

In conclusion, it can be said that the results of the conducted research show that mechanics problems are a powerful didactic tool for developing students' logical thinking. The following conclusions were made:

1) The content and mathematical apparatus of the mechanics section create the most favorable opportunities for the formation of formal-operational thinking in teenage students.

2) Classification of mechanics problems according to the didactic task (qualitative, computational, graphical, experimental, alternative, problematic, combined) allows the teacher to purposefully develop certain logical operations.

3) The five-stage algorithm proposed in the article (perception - symbolization - planning - execution - reflection) teaches the student to solve problems based on a consistent and systematic approach.

4) Heuristic methods - reverse path, schematic drawing, analysis of boundary cases, analogy, problem situations and variational problems - jointly develop different aspects of logical thinking.

5) The effectiveness of the methodology should be assessed not only by the amount of knowledge, but also by the skills of independent thinking, reflection, and knowledge transfer.

In future research, the integration of the proposed methodology with digital educational resources (virtual laboratories, interactive tests, artificial intelligence-based support systems) requires separate study.

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